

RGO/LO Interface Specification

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Introduction

This is a revised version of the file format for 'STAR' data described in NDAC/LO/135. The change concerns the inclusion of two separate magnitude estimates from the IDT photometry: H_1 based on β_1 (the DC component of the light curve) and H_2 based on the modulated component (β_2). The magnitude and colour at OFF = 40 and 42 should be either the original (IC) data or the corresponding data improved by starmapper observations. Note that the colour at OFF = 42 is $B_T - V_T$, not Johnson's $B - V$.

File format for star data

The data type 'STAR' contains the same data as the coordinate file 'COOR', except for the addition of histogram data, a starmapper status word, the position type and magnitude estimates from the IDT photometry. In the file header record, the time of the last observation used to update the star catalogue is also added.

The interface follows the general specifications described in the great-circle reduction programs interface document (GCID-6; Petersen, 14 Aug 1990). The format for the *file label record* is defined in GCID-6, Section 4.4, with

DATAID = 'STAR' IDVERS = 3 LRECHD = 21 LREPGR = 0 IXNRGR = 0.

The *block header record* is defined in GCID-6, Section 4.6.

FILE HEADER RECORD FOR STAR DATA			
NAME	OFF	LEN	DESCRIPTION
LHEADR	0	4	= 4 Number of words in this header record
ICNUMB	4	4	Version number of the star catalogue
ICTYPE	8	4	Type and number of the source catalogue (see GCID-6, Section 6.1)
TLOBS	12	4	Time of the last observation used to update this catalogue (in s since J1988.0)

STAR DATA RECORD			
NAME	OFF	LEN	DESCRIPTION
IDSTAR	0	4	Star identification number
...	...	...	(same as in 'COOR' record)
IFLAGS	47	1	One decimal digit indicating if the star is a variable, or if it is a photometric standard star
NHIST(0)	48	2	Histogram statistics for $\Delta\chi^2$ in bin 0
NHIST(1)	50	2	Histogram statistics for $\Delta\chi^2$ in bin 1
...	...	...	...
NHIST(7)	62	2	Histogram statistics for $\Delta\chi^2$ in bin 7
SMSTAT	64	4	Starmapper status word (see below)
POSTYP	68	4	Position type, i.e., the point in a double or multiple star to which ALPHA, DELTA refer: = 0 for the photocentre or a single star = 1 for the primary (brightest) component = 2 for the secondary component = 3 for the tertiary component, etc = 100 for the geometrical mid-point of a system
HMAG1	72	2	Magnitude H_1 stored as $\text{nint}(10^3 H_1) + 10^4$ or 0 ($H_1 = -10$) if H_1 is undefined
HMAG2	74	2	Magnitude H_2 stored as $\text{nint}(10^3 H_2) + 10^4$ or 0 ($H_2 = -10$) if H_2 is undefined
SDH1	76	2	Standard error of H_1 stored as $\text{nint}(10^3 \sigma_1)$ or 0 if H_1 is undefined; $0 \leq \sigma_1 \leq 32$
SDH2	78	2	Standard error of H_2 stored as $\text{nint}(10^3 \sigma_2)$ or 0 if H_2 is undefined; $0 \leq \sigma_2 \leq 32$
UWVH1	80	2	Unit weight variance of H_1 stored as $\text{nint}(10^3 u_1)$ or 0 if H_1 is undefined; $0 \leq u_1 \leq 32$
UWVH2	82	2	Unit weight variance of H_2 stored as $\text{nint}(10^3 u_2)$ or 0 if H_2 is undefined; $0 \leq u_2 \leq 32$

The first 12 words in the data record are identical to those in data type 'COOR'. The starmapper status word SMSTAT should give information on the observability of the star on the starmapper and flags derived from such observations. Depending on which rejection criteria are used, it could for instance contain the number of rejected starmapper transits in the first two bytes, and the total number of detected transits in the third and fourth bytes.

The word POSTYP tells us how to interpret the catalogue position for a multiple object. It also makes it possible to have one record for each component of a multiple star, distinguished by POSTYP = 1, 2, ..., even if the components have the same star identification number IDSTAR.